

Thermal performance evaluation of a building located in a university campus

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Abstract— Thermal performance analysis and the peak loads calculation of a building offer very important information in the design process and the implementation of a heating system. The paper presents the model developed to evaluate a building located in the campus of a university. The existing heating system of the building based on fossil fuels will be replaced by two geothermal heat pumps. The result of this study is the starting point of the heat pumps design process. A part of the thermal energy generated by the two heat pumps with a total heating capacity overcoming the heating peak load of the target building will be delivered to the heat network of the university. The paper also emphasizes a comparison between the results of a study carried out with TRNSYS software and results obtained within a study performed with Design Builder.

Keywords— thermal performance, thermal load, building simulation, TRNSYS

I. INTRODUCTION

In our country the new codes focus on increasing the energy efficiency of new buildings. However, the building stock still has a great number of units with very deteriorated envelopes, old and deteriorated heating systems with a great energy consumption.

In Romania almost 60% of the buildings were built before 1977 and 85% before 2000. Less than 10% of these buildings were retrofitted by 2020 and it is estimated that 79% will need renovation or even reconstruction by 2050 [1]. The old building stock represents one of the most attractive area for developing energy efficient projects. An energy performance analysis should be carried out before any investment in this kind of buildings. This evaluation offers essential information regarding the energy consumption and appraises the building performance compared to the benchmarks. In this way people interested in analyzed building (owners/tenants) become more motivated in improving its performance.

The energy efficiency of an old building can be increased by applying different retrofitting methods. Thus, an energy consumption reduction generated by any type of initiative (changes of the building envelope [2], changes of the lighting [3], heating systems of the building [4]) is translated to them into lower operation and maintenance costs.

One of these methods consists in changing the heating system without making changes to the building envelope. Replacing a classical heating system based on fossil fuels or

direct electric heating by a heat pump based on renewable sources of energy can reduce the energy consumption of an old building with more than 50%.

II. METHODS USED TO EVALUATE THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF A BUILDING

There are several ways to calculate the thermal energy consumption of an old/new building from the residential/tertiary sector. A common procedure applied to an existing building is the degree-day method. This method estimates the total amount of heat required without taking into consideration the internal heat gains and the radiation. The degree-day number is a characteristic of the buildings depending on the correlation between the climate and the microclimate [5].

Compared with a classic procedure, the methods adopted by the simulation tools take into consideration a greater number of parameters and their variation in time. Parameters such as internal heat gains, solar gains, air infiltration and air ventilation, thermal storage in materials can have a significant influence on the building performance [6], [7].

The simulations methods became available in the 1960s. Originally created in to simulate solar system in 1975, TRNSYS became very popular in the building area [8]. TRNSYS is a graphically based software environment used to simulate the behavior of transient systems. Besides multizone buildings, the library of the software includes a wide range of models representing HVAC equipment, heat pumps, solar collectors, wind turbines and weather data processors [9].

Design Builder or Energy Plus are also very useful environments which allow a complete simulation of a building [10]. Energy Plus is the program of the US DOE (Department of Energy, USA). Design Builder has been developed specifically around Energy Plus and is graphically user interface with a friendly modelling environment.

Typical uses of Design Builder consist of calculating building energy consumption, thermal simulation of naturally ventilated buildings, modelling the lightning control system, designing the cooling and the heating equipment [11].

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE TARGET BUILDING

The studied building (fig. 1) is located in the campus University Politehnica of Bucharest. The building includes laboratories used by the students and offices. This is a two floors old building with an area of 537m².

Fig. 1 Studied building

The thermal energy demand of the studied building is covered by an electrical boiler. The electrical energy necessary to cover the demand of this building is provided by the grid of the university.

The building uses the following heating, cooling, ventilating systems:

- ✓ The electrical boiler with a heating capacity of 110kW connected to a distribution system which includes radiators
- ✓ Air conditioning system consisting of split air conditioners (the system is operated in the offices)
- ✓ A mechanical ventilation system without heating or cooling (the system is operated in the laboratories)
- ✓ An electrical appliance which provides domestic hot water

IV. TRNSYS PROJECT OF THE BUILDING

The target building is involved in a European research project whose purpose is to demonstrate the reliability of renewable heating and cooling district systems. The future heating and cooling system of the building will integrate geothermal and solar sources of energy.

In order to eliminate the deficiencies in the thermal energy supply of the target building and to ensure the thermal comfort conditions combination of two renewable energy (geothermal and solar)-based solutions in a hybrid scheme is proposed.

The aim of the TRNSYS building project is to evaluate the thermal energy demand of the building and to determine the thermal peak loads of this building. Further, the results of the

simulations are used to size the heating capacity of the geothermal heat pumps included in the hybrid system, the distribution system and the fan coils which will be installed in the rooms of the target building. Fig. 2 presents the steps followed to create the project.

Fig. 2 Steps of the simulation process

The building geometry was created in Sketchup/TRNSYS 3d. The model contains 3D geometric surface information which is required for the detailed radiation calculations.

The building is divided into multiple thermal zones. A part of a room, a single room or a group of rooms represent a thermal zone.

The building envelope consists of the following elements: external walls made of different layers of materials such as plasterboard, insulation material (polystyrene and mineral wool with 60mm and 100mm thickness), ground floor and external roof made of concrete.

An overall heat transfer coefficient of 2,8 W/m².K and a solar factor $g=0.755$ are among the main characteristics of the building windows.

Fig. 3. Eastern side of the building

Fig. 4. Western side of the building

The building comprises 22 thermal zones. Each zone is characterized by a certain air volume and thermal capacitance. The thermal zones are naturally ventilated.

The air flow into the zone from the outside of the zone is specified through the number of air changes.

V. RESULTS

Climatic data of the Bucharest city provided by Meteonorm were used to carry out the simulations. Meteonorm contains the information regarding the radiation, air temperature, wind velocity, humidity for a period of one year.

In the thermal zones heated/cooled during the year the temperature is set to 18°C/20°C. These values depend on the activity carried out in the rooms. The maximum temperature is set to 26°C. The simulations were performed for an air changes number of 1.5 1/h. The simulation time step was set to 1 hour.

A. Building evaluation

The graphical representation of the thermal loads shows their evolution within the year. According to fig. 5 the heating load increases from the January to May and then it increases from September to the end of the year. This representation of the demands is useful in establishing the heating/cooling season of the building.

According to the Romanian standards, buildings can be classified depending on their specific energy demand. There are seven energy efficiency classes from class A to class G (A is the highest energy efficiency class while G is the lowest class from the point of view of the energy efficiency).

Table 1 presents a classification of the studied building taking into account the results delivered by TRNSY software and the total surface of the this building.

TABLE 1 BUILDING CLASSIFICATION FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF THE HEATING/COOLING SPECIFIC ENERGY DEMAND

Type of the energy demand	Specific energy demand [kWh/m ² .yr]	Class
Space heating	257	D
Space cooling	23	B

The model is also used to calculate the monthly thermal load of the building (fig. 6). The lowest value of the monthly heating load is achieved in January due to the very low values of the outside temperature achieved within this month.

Fig. 5. Heating and cooling thermal loads of the building (SQh, SQc [kWh])

Fig. 6 Monthly heating/cooling loads

Fig. 7 Peak loads of the building (1 -TRNSYS; 2 – Design Builder)

B. Design of the geothermal heat pumps

Fig. 7 shows the results of the simulations carried out in TRNSYS and Design Builder. According to the simulations there is a very small difference between the values of the peak

demands obtained with the two simulation tools. The heating peak demand achieved with TRNSYS represents 97% of the value obtained with Design Builder [12].

The two geothermal heat pumps included in the hybrid heating system (fig. 8) are sized depending on the heating peak loads delivered by the simulations.

Fig. 8 Solution for thermal energy supply

CONCLUSIONS

TRNSYS and Design Builder are among the simulation tools with a high level of complexity. The two models offer important information regarding the peak load and the thermal performance of the studied building. A comparison of the results shows a difference of 3% regarding the heating load and 1% regarding the cooling load. Two heat pumps of 42 kW, respectively 20.5 kW will be included in the district heating system. The installed thermal energy production capacities will ensure the interior comfort in the spaces within the building as well as the delivery in the centralized heat

supply system of University Politehnica of a heat quota. The future research will be conducted to develop the model of the heating system connected with the building. The TRNSYS model will be used to evaluate the performance and the energy production of this system based on renewable sources of energy.

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